

Muscle activity at different stages of archery shot with changes in finger tab design

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Abstract. This study examines the impact of finger tab design on muscle activity in recurve archers by analyzing electromyographic (EMG) data across different shooting phases. Six elite archers participated, performing shots with and without a pinky hook on the finger tab. The EMG recordings focused on hand, forearm, upper arm, and back muscles involved in the shot execution. Results indicate that finger tab modifications significantly influence muscle tension, particularly in the hand and forearm. The presence of a pinky hook increased muscle activation in the abductor digiti minimi and flexor pollicis brevis, suggesting additional stabilization but also potential premature fatigue. Conversely, shooting without a hook redistributed tension, reducing hand muscle load while slightly increasing activity in other compensatory muscles. During the drawing phase, the flexor pollicis brevis exhibited the highest tension, with increased engagement when the hook was absent. The release phase demonstrated lower muscle activation when using a tab without a hook, potentially facilitating a smoother bowstring release. These findings highlight the importance of individualized equipment customization based on muscle engagement patterns. Proper finger tab selection can optimize performance by balancing grip stability and fatigue prevention, providing valuable insights for archery training and equipment design.

Keywords: muscle activity, bow, finger tab, electromyography, shooting phases

Introduction

The effectiveness of an archer's performance is determined not only by the athlete's skill level but also by their equipment. In recent years, the geography of elite archers on the international stage has significantly expanded, leading to improved athletic performance, approaching absolute values (Dorshorst et al., 2022). Modern materials and approaches to

designing sports bows and related equipment can significantly enhance an archer's performance (Hennessy et al., 1990; Leroyer et al., 1993). With relatively equal levels of athlete preparedness, the technical equipment of the archer plays a crucial role, which is why specialists devote considerable attention to justifying individual tuning of key bow components (Simsek et al., 2018; Pukhov et al., 2024; Stuart et al., 1990). At the same time, the question of finger tab customization remains open, as it provides considerable opportunities for individual adjustment. Modifications to the bow's material components are based on an archer's anthropometric data and current level of physical preparedness. Accordingly, these changes can influence the shooting technique, even though the external movement structure may remain unchanged (Pekalski et al., 1990). Electromyographic (EMG) analysis of sports movements enables an objective assessment of the internal mechanics of technical elements (Ertan et al., 2003), which exhibit significantly greater variability compared to kinematic characteristics (Baifa et al., 2021).

Methods

Thus, the aim of this study was to examine the specific features of muscle tension at different phases of the archery shot when shooting with and without a pinky hook in the finger tab design. The study involved six classical archers with sports qualifications ranging from Candidate for Master of Sport to Master of Sport of Uzbekistan, aged 17–23 years (18.67 ± 0.90 years). All athletes adopted a left-handed stance: the left hand was used for gripping the bow, while the right hand was used to draw the bowstring. During the study, the athletes practiced shooting with a three-finger grip, and their finger tabs included a pinky hook. The archers performed shots at a 3-meter distance while simultaneous electromyographic (EMG) recordings of skeletal muscles were made using the ME-6000 biomonitor (Mega Electronics Ltd., Finland). The EMG recordings included muscles of the right hand and back: flexor pollicis brevis and abductor digiti minimi, flexor digitorum superficialis and extensor digitorum, biceps and triceps brachii, posterior deltoid, and trapezius (upper and lower right-side portions). The EMG amplitude of skeletal muscle activity was analyzed in the technical phases of the shot ("drawing," "holding," and "release") (Moiseev et al., 2024), while modifying the finger tab design (with and without a pinky hook).

When using a finger tab with a hook, the pinky pressed against it; in the grip without a hook, the pinky remained free. Statistical data processing was conducted using Statistica 10.0, calculating the mean (M) and standard error (m). In some cases, percentage changes were computed. The statistical significance of differences in the measured parameters was assessed using one-way repeated measures (ANOVA) with a Newman-Keuls post-hoc analysis.

Results

The analyzed muscles can be divided into two functional groups. The first group consisted of the muscles of the hand and forearm of the drawing arm, which provide grip and release of the bowstring. The second group included the muscles of the upper arm, shoulder girdle, and back, responsible for drawing the bowstring. During bowstring grip, the hand and forearm muscles perform static work and should ideally remain as relaxed as possible to facilitate a smooth release of the bowstring at the moment of the shot (Nishizono et al., 1984). In the drawing phase, the flexor pollicis brevis exhibited the highest tension ($253.63 \pm 21.71 \mu\text{V}$), despite not being in direct contact with the bowstring. Meanwhile, the EMG amplitude of the flexor digitorum superficialis, which directly grips the bowstring by flexing the distal phalanges, was $224.67 \pm 24.34 \mu\text{V}$ (Figure 1). The lowest recorded tensions were in the extensor digitorum ($111.38 \pm 8.21 \mu\text{V}$)—an antagonist to the gripping muscles—and the abductor digiti minimi ($74.92 \pm 3.11 \mu\text{V}$), responsible for gripping the finger tab hook. Modifying the finger tab (by removing the pinky hook) led to a significant increase in flexor pollicis brevis tension in the drawing phase ($345.96 \pm 43.04 \mu\text{V}$, $p < 0.05$), while the EMG amplitude of the abductor digiti minimi significantly decreased to $36.50 \pm 1.06 \mu\text{V}$ ($p < 0.001$) (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – EMG Amplitude of Muscles Involved in Bowstring Grasping

Note. * – significance of differences compared to the previous phase of the shot at $p < 0.05$; # – significance of differences between shots with and without a hook at $p < 0.05$ (## – at $p < 0.001$).

The "draw" phase is predominantly static, as the athlete assumes the primary stance and remains as still as possible. In this phase, the arrow rests on the tip of the arrowhead, and due to the opposing movements of the hands, it is released from the clicker, followed by the release. After the pulling motion performed in the preceding phase, there is a redistribution of muscle tension (Martin et al., 1990) for the static maintenance of the athlete's stance and aiming point. Compared to the tension in the bowstring during the "draw" phase, a decrease in the tension of

the superficial finger flexor by 29.52% ($p < 0.05$) and the short finger flexor by 44.52% ($p < 0.05$) was observed. At the same time, the tension in the muscle that abducts the little finger increased by 14.79% ($p < 0.05$). The exclusion of the hook from the design of the finger tab was accompanied by a significant decrease in the tension of the muscle that abducts the little finger to $40.33 \pm 2.06 \mu\text{V}$ ($p < 0.001$). Additionally, there was a tendency towards an increase in the tension of the superficial finger flexor by 12.74% ($p > 0.05$) and a decrease in the activity of the short thumb flexor by 14.55% ($p > 0.05$) (Figure 1). Thus, in the "draw" phase, there was an increase in the tension of the muscle that abducts the little finger, leading to increased pressure of the little finger on the hook of the finger tab, whereas additional pressure from the fingers on the bowstring is a technical error (Ertan et al., 2009). Conversely, during shots with a finger tab without a hook, the involvement of the little finger in the draw was excluded, but due to load redistribution, there was a slight increase in the activity of the superficial finger flexor.

The release of the arrow should occur by freeing the bowstring from grasping through relaxation of the fingers involved in gripping (Mann et al., 1989). The signal for release is the click of the clicker, after which the arrow lies freely on the shelf (Soylu et al., 2006). In the "release" phase, the EMG amplitude of muscles involved in bowstring grasping was recorded in an average range from 135 to 209 μV (Figure 1). It can be noted that compared to the previous phase (draw), there was a significant increase in tension of the common extensor of fingers by 44.91% ($p < 0.05$) and that of the little finger abductor by 34.95% ($p < 0.05$). When shooting without a hook, during the "release" phase, there was a statistically significant decrease in EMG amplitude of the short thumb flexor to $179.16 \pm 12.53 \mu\text{V}$ ($p < 0.05$) and that of the little finger abductor to $92.91 \pm 4.97 \mu\text{V}$ ($p < 0.001$) compared to shooting with a hook on the finger tab (Figure 1). The absence of a hook in the design of the finger tab was associated with lower tension in muscles involved in grasping the bowstring during the "release" phase. The most significant differences were recorded in activity levels of both the short thumb flexor and little finger abductor muscles. In muscles responsible for bowstring tension, changes in finger tab design did not lead to any significant changes in their average EMG amplitude. Differences were only observed in changes in EMG amplitude during dynamic execution of bow shots (Figure 2). The primary tasks of these muscles are to tension the bowstring and maintain stability in the biomechanical chain "archer-weapon" during aiming. Due to asymmetric loading and maintaining a static position of the shoulder joint during a bow shot, most of, and in some cases excessive, load falls on muscles of the right (drawing) arm and half of the body (Ertan et al., 2005). Throughout all phases of shooting, the greatest tension was developed by the posterior part of the deltoid muscle (Figure 2), which participates in bowstring tensioning and holding a stretched bow by retracting the shoulder backward. Meanwhile, in the "draw" phase, the deltoid muscle demonstrated maximum

average EMG amplitude ($626.42 \pm 154.31 \mu\text{V}$), which was higher compared to its activity in the "tension" and "release" phases by 29.72% ($p < 0.05$) and 25.31% ($p < 0.05$), respectively (Figure 2).

Figure 2 – EMG Amplitude of the Muscles Involved in Drawing the Bowstring

*Note: * – statistical significance of differences compared to the previous shooting phase at $p < 0.05$*

In the lower fibers of the trapezius muscle on the right side, the highest EMG amplitude was also recorded in the "expansion" phase ($350.92 \pm 72.94 \mu\text{V}$), which was 18.65% higher ($p < 0.05$) compared to the "drawing" phase and 7.55% higher ($p > 0.05$) compared to the "release" phase. The tension of the upper fibers of the trapezius muscle did not change significantly throughout the shooting process and remained within the range of 250-300 μV (Figure 2).

The biceps brachii in the "drawing" phase exhibited a tension of $340.67 \pm 79.36 \mu\text{V}$, which decreased to $246.83 \pm 60.7 \mu\text{V}$ ($p < 0.05$) in the "expansion" phase and reached $274.16 \pm 53.51 \mu\text{V}$ ($p > 0.05$) at the moment of arrow release. The highest activity of the biceps brachii during the drawing phase is explained by the active flexion of the pulling arm at the elbow joint.

Among the muscles involved in drawing the bowstring, the triceps brachii developed the lowest tension. In the "drawing" phase, its amplitude was $44.25 \pm 8.21 \mu\text{V}$, while in the "expansion" and "release" phases, it increased to $57.17 \pm 13.83 \mu\text{V}$ ($p < 0.05$) and $64.50 \pm 12.89 \mu\text{V}$ ($p < 0.05$), respectively (Figure 2).

Discussion

The results of this study demonstrated a significant impact of the finger tab design on muscle activity in athletes when shooting with a recurve bow. Specifically, the presence of a hook for the little finger increased the load on the hand muscles, which could have both positive

and negative effects on shooting efficiency. On the one hand, additional fixation may contribute to stabilizing the grip and improving control over the bowstring. On the other hand, increased muscle tension in the hand may lead to premature fatigue and reduced shooting stability during prolonged sessions (Simsek et al., 2018).

An important aspect of this study was identifying changes across the shooting phases. Electromyographic analysis showed that during the drawing phase, the highest tension was observed in the flexor pollicis brevis, whereas the abductor digiti minimi exhibited lower activity. Removing the hook led to a redistribution of the load between these muscles, indicating a high degree of motor control adaptability among athletes. During the expansion phase, there was a general decrease in tension in the primary muscles responsible for gripping the bowstring, while the load on the abductor digiti minimi increased, confirming its crucial role in stabilizing the hook-equipped finger tab (Hamdan et al., 2022; Delahaye et al., 2005).

The arrow release phase proved to be the most indicative stage in terms of the finger tab design's impact on movement biomechanics. The results showed that using a hook-equipped finger tab led to greater tension in the hand, which could make smooth and consistent release more challenging. Conversely, the absence of a hook reduced the load on the hand but increased the activity of other muscles, potentially compensating for the change in grip (Ertan et al., 2021).

Comparing the obtained data with previous studies on archery biomechanics, it is evident that the influence of finger tab design remains an underestimated factor in athlete training. Most research focuses on kinematic movement parameters, whereas electromyographic activity analysis provides deeper insight into the underlying movement control mechanisms. The findings of this study may have practical significance for customizing athletes' equipment, as finger tab selection should take into account not only the archer's subjective preferences but also objective indicators of muscle tension.

From a practical perspective, our results highlight the importance of an individualized approach to equipment selection. For example, athletes prone to hand fatigue may benefit from a finger tab without a hook, whereas archers struggling with bowstring control might find the hook more advantageous. Future research in this field could explore the effects of other design features of finger tabs, as well as the influence of different training methods on muscle adaptation to equipment changes.

Conclusion

Executing a shot with a recurve bow was accompanied by significant dynamics in muscle tension changes as the shooting phases transitioned, which was determined by the types of muscle contractions in each phase.

Shooting without a little finger hook on the finger tab resulted in a significant reduction in the tension of the abductor digiti minimi muscle across all examined technical phases. This suggests that when a hook is present, the little finger applies pressure to it, increasing tension in the hand, whereas the muscles should primarily focus on gripping the bowstring without additional force. In contrast, when shooting without a hook, the little finger's involvement in gripping the bowstring was minimized.

Modifications in the finger tab design did not affect the muscle tension of those involved in drawing the bowstring.

References

1. Ertan, H. Muscular activation patterns of the bow arm in recurve archery. *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport*. 2009;12(3), 357–360. doi:10.1016/j.jsams.2008.01.003.
2. Simsek, D., Cerrah, A. O., Ertan, H., & Soylu, R. A. Muscular coordination of movements associated with arrow release in archery. *South African Journal for Research in Sport, Physical Education and Recreation*. 2018;40(1), 141–155.
3. Dorshorst, T., Weir, G., Hamill, J., & Holt, B. Archery's signature: an electromyographic analysis of the upper limb. *Evolutionary Human Sciences*. 2022;4:1-20. doi:10.1017/ehs.2022.20
4. Baifa, Z., Xinglong, Z., & Dongmei, L. Muscle coordination during archery shooting: A comparison of archers with different skill levels. *European Journal of Sport Science*. 2021; 23(1):1-14, 54–61. doi:10.1080/17461391.2021.2014573.
5. Ertan, H., Kentel, B. B., Tümer, S. T., & Korkusuz, F. Activation patterns in forearm muscles during archery shooting. *Human Movement Science*. 2003; Feb;22(1):37-45. doi: 10.1016/s0167-9457(02)00176-8.
6. Pukhov, A. M., & Tarnakov, D. P. Features of muscle activity in different phases of bow shot with changes in the design of the finger tab. *Science and Sport*. 2024;12(2), 45–52. doi: 10.36028/2308-8826-2024-12-2-50-55
7. Moiseev, S. A., Pukhov, A. M., & Gorodnichev, R. M. Features of synergistic interaction of skeletal muscles during archery with different finger tab designs. *Science and Sport*. 2024; 12(2), 53–60. doi:10-36028/2308-8826-2024-12-2-42-49.
8. Ertan, H., Soylu, A. R., & Korkusuz, F. Quantification the relationship between FITA scores and EMG skill indexes in archery. *Journal of Electromyography and Kinesiology*. 2005; Apr;15(2):222-7. doi: 10.1016/j.jelekin.2004.08.004.
9. Soylu, A. R., Ertan, H., & Korkusuz, F. Archery performance level and repeatability of event-related EMG. *Human Movement Science*. 2006; Dec;25(6):767-74. doi: 10.1016/j.humov.2006.05.002.

10. Martin, P. E., Siler, W. L., & Hoffman, D. Electromyographic analysis of bowstring release in highly skilled archers. *Journal of Sports Sciences*. 1990; 8(3):215-21. doi: 10.1080/02640419008732147.
11. Hennessy, M. P., & Parker, A. W. Electromyography of arrow release in archery. *Electromyography and Clinical Neurophysiology*. 1990; 30(1), 7–17.
12. Leroyer, P., Hoecke, J. V., & Helal, N. Biomechanical study of the final push-pull in archery. *Journal of Sports Sciences*. 1993; Feb;11(1):63-9. doi: 10.1080/02640419308729965.
13. Nishizono, H., Nakagawa, K., Suda, T., & Yamasaki, N. An electromyographical analysis of purposive muscle activity and appearance of muscle silent period in archery shooting. *Japanese Journal of Physical Fitness and Sports Medicine*. 1984; Volume 33 Issue 1 Pages 17-26. doi: 10.7600/jspfsm1949.33.17
14. Mann, D. L., & Littke, N. Shoulder injuries in archery. *Canadian Journal of Sport Sciences*. 1989; 14(2), 85–92.
15. Stuart, J., & Atha, J. Postural consistency in skilled archers. *Journal of Sports Sciences*. 1990; 8(3):223-34. doi: 10.1080/02640419008732148.
16. Pekalski, R. Experimental and theoretical research in archery. *Journal of Sports Sciences*. 1990; 8(3):259-79. doi: 10.1080/02640419008732150.
17. Delahaye, H., Tomaszewski, A., Diard, J., Olivier, V., & Vanvelcenaher, J. The shoulder of the archer: Clinical, video and isokinetic evaluation. *Isokinetics and Exercise Science*. 2005; 13(2), 81–86.
18. Ertan, H., Yagcioglu, S., Yilmaz, A., Urgan, P., & Korkusuz, F. Accuracy in archery shooting is linked to the amplitude of the ERP N1 to the snap of clicker. *Montenegrin Journal of Sports Science and Medicine*. 2021;10(1), 37–44. doi:10.26773/mjssm.210306.
19. Hamdan, Z., Zulkifli, A., & Nasrul, J. Investigation of muscle fatigue of the archer's during endurance shooting. *Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Sciences*. 2022; 16(3), 8987–8995. doi:10.15282/jmes.16.3.2022.02.0711.
20. Simsek, D., Cerrah, A. O., Ertan, H., & Soylu, R. A. Muscular coordination of movements associated with arrow release in archery. *South African Journal for Research in Sport, Physical Education and Recreation*. 2018; 40(1), 141–155.